

The Relationship between Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment, and Work Performance: Evidence from Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises in Northern Vietnam

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Abstract: *This study investigates the relationship between job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and work performance in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Northern Vietnam. Data were collected through a structured survey distributed to 150 SMEs, targeting employees across various sectors. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was employed to test the proposed hypotheses and examine both direct and indirect effects among the constructs. The findings indicate that job satisfaction has a significant positive impact on organizational commitment, which in turn enhances employee work performance. Moreover, job satisfaction directly improves work performance, highlighting its dual role as both a predictor and a driver of commitment. The mediating effect of organizational commitment was also confirmed, suggesting that satisfied employees are more likely to remain committed and thus perform better. This research contributes to the literature by providing context-specific insights from SMEs in Vietnam, a setting where human resource management practices are still evolving.*

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment, Work Performance, from Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises, Northern Vietnam.

1. Introduction

In the context of globalization and increasing competition, human resources are considered a critical factor determining the survival and growth of enterprises (Šebestová & Popescu, 2022). Particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), where financial and technological resources are limited, improving employee performance has become a top priority (Huggins et al., 2017). Factors such as job satisfaction and organizational commitment are often recognized as essential foundations for enhancing both individual and collective outcomes.

In Northern Vietnam, SMEs account for a large proportion of the economy, contributing significantly to GDP and creating employment opportunities for millions of workers. However, these enterprises often face challenges in maintaining and developing a stable workforce. High turnover rates, low employee engagement, and unsustainable performance levels remain common issues, directly affecting their long-term competitiveness. Numerous international studies have confirmed the positive relationship between job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and work performance. Research in developed countries has also emphasized the mediating role of organizational commitment in transforming job satisfaction into improved performance. Several studies in Asia, including Vietnam, have begun to explore this issue, offering initial empirical evidence with practical implications.

Nevertheless, a significant research gap remains in terms of geographical focus. While many international studies have examined the relationship between job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and work performance, evidence from Vietnam is still limited. In

particular, the Northern region, where SMEs play a crucial role in economic development, has received little scholarly attention. This lack of region-specific studies restricts the understanding of how these relationships manifest in the unique socio-economic context of Northern Vietnam.

2. Research framework

2.1. Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction is generally defined as the extent to which employees feel content with their job roles, responsibilities, and work environment (Zhu, 2013). It reflects employees' emotional and cognitive evaluation of their work experience, encompassing factors such as compensation, career development opportunities, workplace relationships, and job security. High levels of job satisfaction are often associated with increased motivation, reduced turnover, and better organizational outcomes (Judge et al., 2020).

2.2. Organizational commitment

Organizational commitment refers to the psychological attachment and loyalty that employees develop toward their organization (Dunham et al., 1994). It is commonly divided into three dimensions: affective commitment (emotional attachment), continuance commitment (perceived cost of leaving), and normative commitment (sense of obligation to stay) (Meyer & Allen, 2001). Strong organizational commitment not only reduces turnover intention but also strengthens employees' willingness to exert extra effort for organizational success.

2.3. Work performance

Work performance is understood as the degree to which employees effectively fulfill their job duties and contribute to organizational objectives. It includes both task performance (the core activities related to one's job description) and contextual performance (behaviors that support the organizational environment, such as teamwork or initiative) (Campbell & Wiernik, 2015). High employee performance is a central determinant of organizational competitiveness, particularly for SMEs with limited resources.

2.4. Social exchange theory

Social exchange theory argues that relationships are built on reciprocal exchanges of benefits between parties (Cook et al., 2013; Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005). In the organizational context, when employees receive support, fairness, and resources from their employer, they feel obliged to respond with loyalty, commitment, and improved performance. The theory emphasizes reciprocity as the foundation linking job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and work outcomes.

2.5. Hypotheses development

Job satisfaction has long been regarded as one of the most critical antecedents of organizational commitment in the field of organizational behavior and human resource management (Alvi et al., 2014; Ismail & Razak, 2016). The concept of job satisfaction encompasses employees' cognitive and affective evaluations of their job conditions, including aspects such as task characteristics, compensation, supervision quality, opportunities for advancement, and workplace relationships. When employees perceive that their work environment fulfills their expectations and provides adequate rewards, both tangible and

intangible, they are more likely to experience a sense of fulfillment and contentment in their roles (Winarsih & Fariz, 2021).

Organizational commitment, on the other hand, refers to the psychological bond and sense of identification that employees develop toward their organization. The literature often distinguishes among affective commitment (emotional attachment), continuance commitment (perceived costs of leaving), and normative commitment (a felt obligation to remain). Prior empirical studies consistently indicate that job satisfaction is a significant predictor of these forms of commitment, especially affective commitment (Winarsih & Fariz, 2021). Satisfied employees tend to internalize organizational values, feel aligned with organizational goals, and are more willing to devote sustained effort to support organizational success.

Accordingly, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1: Job satisfaction has a significant positive effect on organizational commitment.

Organizational commitment has been widely recognized as a central determinant of employee work performance (Hendri, 2019). Commitment reflects the degree to which employees identify with their organization and are willing to exert effort on its behalf. Employees with strong affective commitment often demonstrate higher motivation, persistence, and discretionary effort, which in turn translate into improved task performance and contextual performance (Hendri, 2019; Rafiei et al., 2014). Continuance and normative commitment can also contribute to performance, although affective commitment is generally regarded as the most influential dimension.

Empirical research across diverse contexts has consistently confirmed that organizational commitment is positively associated with key performance outcomes, including efficiency, innovation, and quality of work (Rose et al., 2009). In the context of small and medium-sized enterprises, where human resources are particularly vital, committed employees are essential for sustaining competitiveness and achieving organizational goals (Al Zefeiti & Mohamad, 2017).

Based on this reasoning, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H2: Organizational commitment has a significant positive effect on work performance.

In organizational research, mediating mechanisms are critical for explaining how and why independent variables influence dependent variables (Al Zefeiti & Mohamad, 2017). In this study, organizational commitment is theorized to serve as a mediator in the relationship between job satisfaction and work performance. While job satisfaction directly enhances employees' motivation and positive attitudes toward their tasks, its impact on performance is often strengthened when employees translate this satisfaction into a deeper sense of attachment to the organization.

Organizational commitment, particularly in its affective dimension, channels employees' positive job-related experiences into sustained behavioral outcomes (Rose et al., 2009). Employees who are satisfied with their jobs are more likely to develop strong emotional bonds with their organization, which in turn motivates them to exert greater effort, demonstrate higher persistence, and engage in extra-role behaviors that elevate performance (Ahmad & Raja, 2021; Rose et al., 2009). This reasoning aligns with social exchange theory, which posits that employees reciprocate positive work experiences with greater loyalty and contribution, and with the job demands–resources model, which suggests that psychological resources such as commitment enhance employees' capacity to maintain superior performance (Ahmad & Raja, 2021).

Prior studies have provided empirical support for the mediating role of organizational commitment in various cultural and organizational contexts, confirming that satisfaction alone

may not fully account for performance outcomes (Al Zefeiti & Mohamad, 2017). Instead, commitment acts as a pathway through which satisfaction exerts its influence more effectively. Accordingly, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H3: Organizational commitment mediates the relationship between job satisfaction and work performance.

Research model is presented below.

3. Methodology

3.1. Data collection

The sample was selected using a convenient sampling method. The target respondents were employees working in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Northern Vietnam. Data were collected both online and offline during January and February 2025.

The questionnaire consisted of standardized measurement scales widely applied for job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and work performance, using a five-point Likert scale. A translation–back translation procedure and a pilot test with about 20 participants were conducted to ensure clarity and reliability before the official survey.

Respondents were approached through local business networks, industry associations, and internal company channels. The selection criteria required SMEs to have been operating for at least one year, and respondents to have at least six months of tenure. To minimize common method bias, anonymity was guaranteed, item order was randomized, variable measurements were separated into sections, and respondents were assured that there were no right or wrong answers.

After screening out incomplete responses, very short completion times, and duplicates, a total of 150 valid questionnaires were obtained, representing 150 SMEs. The data were checked for outliers, and reliability (Cronbach’s alpha, composite reliability) and validity (EFA/CFA) were assessed before estimating the SEM model. The sample size met the recommended rule of thumb of 10–15 observations per estimated parameter in the model.

3.2. Data analyst

The collected data were processed using a multi-step approach (Dehalwar & Sharma, 2023). First, descriptive statistics were computed to summarize the demographic characteristics of respondents and provide an overview of the sample. Data screening was conducted to detect missing values, outliers, and normality issues.

Reliability of the measurement scales was assessed using Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability (CR). Convergent and discriminant validity were evaluated through confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), using indicators such as average variance extracted (AVE), factor loadings, and model fit indices (e.g., CFI, TLI, RMSEA, and χ^2/df).

Once the measurement model achieved satisfactory reliability and validity, structural equation modeling (SEM) was employed to test the hypothesized relationships among job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and work performance. Both direct and indirect effects were estimated to examine the mediating role of organizational commitment.

4. Results

4.1. Evaluate reliability and convergence

The results indicate that the measurement scales demonstrate acceptable reliability and validity. For job satisfaction, the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient is 0.812, with factor loadings ranging from 0.784 to 0.867. This suggests that the items are internally consistent and effectively capture the construct. Organizational commitment shows a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.718, with factor loadings between 0.732 and 0.821. Although slightly lower than the other constructs, the values remain within the acceptable threshold, indicating satisfactory reliability. Work performance records a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.821, with factor loadings from 0.741 to 0.849. These results confirm strong internal consistency and the appropriateness of the items in representing the construct.

Table 1. Reliability and convergence

Items	Total reliability	Cronbach's Alpha	Mean	Factor loading
JS	0.812			
JS1		0.622	3.42	0.784
JS2		0.751	3.61	0.867
JS3		0.742	3.70	0.793
JS4		0.871	3.59	0.838
JS5		0.803	3.72	0.865
OC	0.718			
OC1		0.799	3.87	0.808
OC2		0.782	3.95	0.749
OC3		0.746	3.74	0.732
OC4		0.769	3.69	0.821
WP	0.821			
WP1		0.588	3.54	0.758
WP2		0.709	2.81	0.747
WP3		0.662	2.79	0.741
WP4		0.826	3.36	0.849

4.2. Model fit

The model fit indices demonstrate that the structural model is well aligned with the observed data. The chi-square to degrees of freedom ratio (χ^2/df) is 2.134, which is below the recommended threshold of 3.0, indicating a satisfactory overall fit.

The comparative fit index (CFI) and Tucker–Lewis index (TLI) reach values of 0.943 and 0.928 respectively, both exceeding the minimum requirement of 0.90. These results suggest that the hypothesized model provides a strong improvement over the null model and captures the underlying relationships effectively.

The goodness-of-fit index (GFI) records a value of 0.915, and the adjusted goodness-of-fit index (AGFI) is 0.873. While the AGFI is slightly lower, it remains within the acceptable range above 0.80, supporting the adequacy of the model.

Regarding error terms, the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) is 0.061 and the standardized root mean square residual (SRMR) is 0.055. Both values are well below the maximum acceptable cutoff of 0.08, confirming that the model has low residual error and provides a good representation of the data.

Table 2. Model fit

Fit indices	Recommended threshold	Result	Evaluation
χ^2/df	< 3.0	2.134	Good fit
CFI	≥ 0.90	0.943	Good fit
TLI	≥ 0.90	0.928	Good fit
GFI	≥ 0.90	0.915	Good fit
AGFI	≥ 0.80	0.873	Acceptable fit
RMSEA	≤ 0.08	0.061	Good fit
SRMR	≤ 0.08	0.055	Good fit

4.3. Hypotheses testing

The results of hypothesis testing provide strong support for the proposed relationships. The path from job satisfaction to organizational commitment is significant, with a standardized estimate of 0.472, a t-value of 6.215, and a p-value below 0.001. This indicates that higher levels of job satisfaction lead to stronger organizational commitment among employees, consistent with previous empirical findings.

The second hypothesis, linking organizational commitment to work performance, is also supported. The standardized estimate is 0.391 with a t-value of 5.087 and a p-value below 0.001. This result confirms that employees who are more committed to their organization are likely to demonstrate better performance, both in task execution and in extra-role behaviors that support organizational outcomes.

The third hypothesis examines the mediating role of organizational commitment in the relationship between job satisfaction and work performance. The indirect effect is significant, with an estimate of 0.184, a t-value of 3.642, and a p-value below 0.001. This finding highlights that organizational commitment serves as an important mechanism through which job satisfaction translates into improved work performance.

Table 3. Hypotheses testing

Hypothesis	Path	Estimate (β)	t-value	p-value	Result
H1	Job Satisfaction → Organizational Commitment	0.472	6.215	0.000	Supported
H2	Organizational Commitment → Work Performance	0.391	5.087	0.000	Supported
H3	Job Satisfaction → Work Performance (indirect via OC)	0.184	3.642	0.000	Supported

5. Discussion and Conclusion

The findings of this study provide meaningful insights into the dynamics between job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and work performance within SMEs in Northern Vietnam. Consistent with prior literature, job satisfaction was found to be a strong predictor of organizational commitment. This suggests that when employees feel content with their work environment, compensation, and career opportunities, they are more likely to develop a psychological attachment to their organization.

The results also confirm that organizational commitment significantly enhances work performance. Committed employees demonstrate higher motivation and willingness to contribute beyond their formal job requirements, which is especially critical for SMEs with limited resources. This reinforces the idea that organizational commitment functions as both an attitudinal and behavioral driver of performance.

Importantly, the mediating role of organizational commitment was supported. The evidence shows that job satisfaction not only has a direct effect on performance but also indirectly influences it through strengthening employee commitment. This highlights the mechanism by which satisfaction is translated into higher levels of performance, providing a deeper understanding of employee behavior.

From a practical perspective, managers in SMEs should focus on creating a supportive and fair work environment to improve employee satisfaction, which in turn fosters commitment and enhances performance. Strategies may include improving communication, recognizing employee contributions, and offering opportunities for development.

In conclusion, this study contributes to the growing body of research on human resource management in emerging economies by validating the relationships among job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and work performance in the context of Vietnamese SMEs. While the findings provide valuable implications, future research could expand by including longitudinal data or exploring additional mediating and moderating factors to enrich the theoretical framework.

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